

Web-Based Information System Analysis and Design

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Abstract— A good information system design will make an organization more effective and efficient in running its organization. An information system is a system that connects the needs of daily transaction processing, operation support, management activities, and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports, both for internal and certain external parties. One application of information systems in an organization is to design a web-based application. Web-based applications are often used to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of activity. The process of designing web-based applications using software such as PHP and supported by a MySQL database. The design of a web-based information system can solve problems in an organization effectively and efficiently, including a web-based information system that can eliminate repetition of activities in the Process Laboratory IV PT X, a web-based information system can be used to tourism marketing efficiently in the case study of the Pulau Wisata Biduk, and a web-based information system can manage a warehouse better, accountable and transparent on a CV. ABB.

Index Terms— Database, Information System, MySQL, PHP, Web Based Application

I. INTRODUCTION

A good information system design will make an organization more effective and efficient in running its organization. Especially the manufacturing industry organizations that will not be separated from information systems. The implementation of an effective information system for a manufacturing industry organization will facilitate the organization in managing and controlling its production system. However, information systems that are too complex and complicated can reduce the efficiency of the overall production system [1].

One application of information systems in an organization is to design a web-based application. Web-based applications can be applied in broad scope, including to increase efficiency in the learning process, consumption of electrical energy at home, the process of collecting survey data, and can be used as marketing a product or service. This increase in efficiency occurs because web-based applications make it easier for actors involved in the system to carry out their tasks [1].

Web-based applications are often used to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of activity [3] such as Azwir and Patriani (2017) who designed information systems to improve

warehousing management at CV. ABB using PHP and MySQL, Yuliandra and Wulan (2018) designed an information system by creating web-based applications for quality control at the PT X process IV laboratory, and Amrina, et al (2019) who designed an information system by making mobile web applications for marketing. tour guide.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Information System

The definition of an information system can be derived from each of its constituent words, namely system, and information. Anggraini and Zega (2008) define a system as a collection of several elements or elements that interact with each other to achieve a certain goal. A similar definition is also given by Jogiyanto (2005) who describes the system as a network of interconnected work to perform an activity or complete a particular goal. Systems can be groups of people, machines, things, or other types of entities. Meanwhile, information can be defined as the result of data processing that has a certain value or meaning. Based on the definitions of these two words, Leitch and Davis (2005) define an information system as a system that connects the needs of daily transaction processing, operations support, management activities, and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports, both for internal and external purposes. beyond certain [3].

An information system is the result of human design and consists of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, namely to provide useful information. An information system is one of the aspects needed by the organization. The general objectives of the information system include: (1) Providing information that can assist the management decision-making process; (2) Facilitate the implementation of daily operations; and (3) Providing appropriate information for parties outside the organization, especially regarding the issue of management transparency [3].

Sutabri (2005) says that the value of information is based on ten properties, namely [6]

1. Easy to get

This property shows the ease and speed of information that can be obtained.

2. Spacious and complete

This characteristic indicates the completeness of the information content, not only regarding the volume but also regarding the output of the information.

3. Accuracy

This property is related to the degree of freedom from error information output.

4. Compatibility

This property shows how well the information output corresponds to the user's request.

5. Punctuality

This property relates to the time elapsed for input, processing, and reporting of output to users which is shorter than the cycle for obtaining information.

6. Clarity

This property indicates the level of information output that is free from unclear terms.

7. Dexterity

This property relates to the adaptability of information output to more than one decision.

8. Can be proven

This trait indicates the ability of multiple users of the information to test the output and arrive at the same conclusion.

9. No prejudice

This trait is related to the lack of desire to change

10. Measurable

This property shows the nature of the information generated from formal information systems in order to obtain previously considered conclusions.

In an information system, there are components such as [4]

1. Hardware: Includes physical devices such as computers and printers.
2. Software or Program: A set of instructions that enable the hardware to process data.
3. Procedure: A set of rules used to achieve data processing and the generation of the desired output.
4. People: All parties responsible for information system development, processing, and use of information system output.
5. Database: A collection of tables, relationships, and others related to data storage.
6. Computer Networks and Data Communications: Liaison systems that allow resources to be shared or accessed by a number of users.

B. Database

McLeod (2008) argues that a database can be defined as a collection of data that is integrated, organized, and stored in a way so that it can be retrieved easily. A similar explanation is also given by Vanny and Syahyuman (2012) who define a database as a collection of data that is processed computerized into a piece of interconnected and organized information that can be obtained quickly and easily. Jogiyanto (2005) argues that the main function of the database is to provide information for its users. Databases in information systems are used as: (1) a place to store data and information; (2) A tool to process data and provide reports related to stored data or information [1].

Sutabri (2005) defines a database as a collection of connected data that is stored together on a media, without the need for data replication in a certain way so that it is easy to reuse, can be used by one or more application programs optimally, data is

stored without experiencing dependence on a program that will use it, the data is stored in such a way that addition, retrieval, and modification can be done easily and controlled [6].

According to Sutabri (2005), the definition of the database concludes that the database has several important criteria, namely [6]

1. It is data-oriented and not program-oriented
2. Can be used by several application programs without changing the database.
3. Can expand easily both in volume and structure.
4. Can meet the needs of new systems easily.
5. Can be used in different ways.
6. Minimum data collection.

Connolly and Begg (2010) argue that database design is a process that produces a detailed data model of the database, database design involves selecting: columns for each table and how the tables and columns interact with each other. The term database design can function as an application of the overall design process, not only on the structure of the database but also the queries and forms that function as part of the overall database in a database management system [5].

C. PHP and MySQL

The application design process uses software such as PHP and is supported by a MySQL database. PHP stands for Hypertext Preprocessor which is a programming language that is used to build dynamic websites. PHP is a web programming language in the form of a script that can be integrated with HTML [2]. PHP is integrated with HTML code that the meaning is different conditions. HTML is used as a builder or foundation of a web layout framework, while PHP is used as a process so that with PHP, the web will be very easy to maintain. PHP is also built as a module on the Apache webserver and as a binary that can run as CGI [3].

MySQL is a database management system. A database is a structured collection of data. The data can be anything, from a simple list to an image gallery. To add, access, and process data stored in a database, a database management system such as MySQL is needed. Since the computer has become a tool used to deal with large amounts of data, database management plays a major role in calculations, as a single utility, or as part of other applications [3].

III. DISCUSSION

Yuliandra and Wulan (2018) in their case study research designed a new information system at the Process Laboratory IV PT X, as well as supporting web-based applications with the aim of more efficient quality control. Information system analysis at Process Laboratory IV PT X begins with testing samples using X-ray and QCX machines, processing data using spreadsheet software, and reporting results to evaluation staff and Central Control Panel (CCP) operators. Based on the observations, there is a repetition of data input activity by operator 1 that occurs because the CCP operator is only allowed to access part of the contents of the report. In addition, by using spreadsheet software there is the possibility of fraud committed by actors in the system. Therefore, a web-based application was

designed which not only served as a substitute for spreadsheets but also provided improvements to the information system used. The new information system at the Process Laboratory IV PT X eliminates the repetition of setpoint data input activities that are usually carried out by Operator 1. Elimination of these activities will reduce the time required to carry out the entire process, thereby increasing system efficiency. In addition, the elimination of repetition will also minimize the potential for human errors and writing errors in the data input process.

The design of a web-based information system was also carried out by Amrina, et al (2019) in their case study entitled Design of a Car Web-Based Island Tourism Biduk Marketing Information System. The purpose of designing this web-based information system is to provide more effective product marketing through internet media to disseminate information about island tourism transportation services on Pisang Island so that it can be widely known and can provide economic benefits for the fishing community of the Big Dipper on the Pisang River. This marketing information system is designed using the PHP programming language. Data related to island tourism in Sungai Pisang is collected and stored in a database designed using MySQL. The design of this marketing information system is expected to be able to increase the number of tourists who use the island in an effort to increase the economy of the fishermen in a sustainable way.

Azwir and Patriani (2017) also designed a web-based information system to improve warehouse management on a CV. ABB. Warehousing Management at CV. ABB is currently not very good, such as warehouse data collection, part request data, spare part stock data, spare part expenditure data, and purchase order data which is still very manual. Therefore, it is necessary to design a web-based information system to improve warehousing management so that the warehouse management in CV. ABB can be better, accountable, and transparent. PHP and MySQL are open source tools in the development of web-based information systems that are used to overcome this problem.

IV. CONCLUSION

The design of a web-based information system can solve problems in an organization effectively and efficiently, including a web-based information system that can eliminate repetition of activities in the Process Laboratory IV PT X, a web-based information system can be used to tourism marketing efficiently in the case study of the Pulau Wisata Biduk, and a web-based information system can manage to warehouse better, be accountable and transparent on a CV. ABB.

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